

MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ nanorods synthesized using NiO nanoparticles for hydrogen evolution in anion exchange membrane water electrolysis[☆]

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Anion exchange membrane
Water electrolysis
Hydrogen evolution
Non PGM materials
Synthesis scale up

ABSTRACT

The development of sustainable catalysts for anion exchange membrane water electrolyzers (AEMWE) has attracted considerable attention in recent years due to the possibility of using earth abundant elements to replace platinum group metals (e.g. Pt, Ru, Ir) as catalysts. One class of promising materials for the hydrogen evolution reaction are nickel-molybdenum compounds. Here we present a novel method for preparing Mo-Ni based catalysts with high dispersion using commercially available NiO nanoparticles as seeds. A complete physical and morphological characterization indicates that the NiO particles act as nucleation centers for the growth of NiMoO₄ nanorods. During high temperature reductive annealing, a MoO_{3-x} rich layer forms on the surface of the rods. Electrochemical measurements demonstrate enhanced performance when compared to the analogous material produced using Ni foam. The powder catalyst was applied to a membrane electrode assembly using a catalyst coated substrate technique and tests in AEMWEs were carried out with electrodes of 78.5 cm² area. A current density of 1 A cm⁻² at a cell voltage of 1.8 V was obtained when coupled with an IrO₂ anode. When combined with a non PGM NiCo₂O₄ anode, 1 A cm⁻² of electrolysis current density was produced at 2.0 V.

1. Introduction

Molecular hydrogen (H₂) is a promising energy vector that can be employed to store intermittent renewable energy through water electrolysis [1]. The current state of the art in water electrolysis is the proton exchange membrane water electrolyser (PEMWE). For PEM electrolyzers, the critical raw materials (CRMs) iridium, titanium and platinum are required as catalyst materials to maintain sufficient stability due to the highly acidic environment created by the membrane [2] as well as high anodic potentials. Hence, the natural abundance of CRMs will be a crucial factor in the development of electrolyser and fuel cell technologies for use in a large scale hydrogen economy [1]. Operation under alkaline conditions of an electrolyzer with a membrane that transports anions (anion exchange membrane (AEM)), creates the possibility of utilizing less expensive and more abundant materials [3–6]. A recent

comparison of hydrogen production using AEM and PEM electrolysis has shown that both technologies have a similar life-cycle environmental profile [7]. However, AEM electrolysis shows significantly lower raw material criticality since it does not rely on platinum-group metals. Overall, a promising environmental and material criticality performance of AEM electrolysis for hydrogen production was concluded [7]. The performance of AEMWEs on a laboratory scale is promising [8] with current densities of up to 7.68 A cm⁻² achieved at 2 V cell potential [9]. Regarding the Hydrogen Evolution Reaction (HER), Pt remains the state-of-the-art material. Research into developing alternative more sustainable HER electrocatalysts based on more abundant and cheaper elements is ongoing [5]. Recent examples of such materials are nickel-molybdenum compounds [11] that exhibit the best HER catalytic performance among all the non-noble metal-based materials. Recent comprehensive review papers discuss in detail the state of the art in Ni-

[☆] This article is part of a special issue entitled: 'HYCELTEC2024' published in Chemical Engineering Journal.

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.162026>

Available online 27 March 2025

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Mo compounds for the HER [10,12,13]. A number of different nanostructures and compositions have been reported [12–16]. Notably, high HER activity has been reported for catalysts based on $\text{MoNi}_4/\text{MoO}_{3-x}$ nanorod arrays [17,18]. Such nanorod arrays are generally formed through solvothermal synthesis on the surface of a nickel foam electrode support. After high temperature treatment (500–600 °C) under a reducing gas atmosphere ($\text{H}_2\text{-N}_2$ mix), the surface of the nanorods is roughened and HER active phases such as Ni_4Mo and MoO_2 are segregated to the surface. Previously, we have reported a HER catalyst composed of Ni foam supported nanorods with the surface composed of a MoO_2 rich layer [19]. The activity of Ni-Mo catalysts originates from the heterogenic interfaces of such alloy-oxides or alloy-hydroxides, in which the oxide or hydroxide promotes water dissociation and the alloy accelerates hydrogen combination [12,13]. Ni foam based electrodes are limited by the nature of the solid support that allows only a small portion of the material to be coated with the active phase with the remaining bulk nickel foam not active. Consequently, a powder catalyst consisting of only the Ni-Mo active phase would have a significantly higher mass specific activity. In this article we report the development of a new synthesis method for preparing a Mo-Ni powder catalyst composed solely of nanorod particles, using commercially available NiO nanopowder as substrate. Commercially available NiO nanoparticles are used as “seed” for growth of the Mo-Ni nanostructures. Complete physical (HR-TEM, SEM, XPS, Raman) and electrochemical characterization is reported. In-situ and ex-situ Raman spectroscopy indicate the formation of a surface rich in MoO_{3-x} active phases. Samples were prepared at two different temperatures (500 and 600 °C) to probe the best synthesis conditions. Results confirm the best material forms at 600 °C during synthesis and this catalyst powder was applied to a 78.5 cm^2 disk electrode using a catalyst coated substrate technique. Tested in a large AEM electrolyser, at a current density of 1 A cm^{-2} , a stable cell voltage of 1.8 V was observed with an IrO_2 anode and at 2.0 V with a NiCo_2O_4 anode. By comparison, the nickel foam supported catalyst reported in our previous article operated at a current density of 0.5 A cm^{-2} at 1.85 V cell potential, highlighting the advantage of the new synthesis method described here. A powder catalyst that consists of only the active phase when used in an electrolyser produces twice as much current density at the same cell voltage.

2. Experimental section

All metal salts and reagents were purchased from Merck and used as received. All the solutions were freshly prepared with doubly distilled deionized water. The fumasep FAA-3-PK130 membrane and ionomer FAA-3-FILM were purchased from Fumatech GmbH (Germany).

2.1. Catalyst synthesis

The catalyst powder denoted $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ was prepared using a two-step synthesis. Firstly, 1.2 mmol of $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and 0.3 mmol of $(\text{NH}_4)_6\text{Mo}_7\text{O}_{24} \cdot 0.4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were mixed together with 100 mg of NiO nanopowder 98.8 % (particle size < 50 nm (TEM)) in 60 ml of distilled water. The solution was then sonicated for 30 mins to suspend the NiO nanopowder. The black suspension thus obtained was sealed inside a PTFE lined autoclave and heated at 150 °C for 6 h. The resulting yellow precipitate denoted as (NiMoO_4) was then filtered, washed with water and dried at 70 °C. Finally, the MoNiO_4 precursor was placed inside a rotating quartz oven (Carbolyte Gero TSO 11/400), purged for 30 min with N_2 then heated to either 500 or 600 °C at 10 °C min^{-1} for 2 h under a flow of the gas mixture $\text{H}_2:\text{N}_2$ (5:95, v/v) with a flow rate of 0.5 slm; the furnace was then cooled down to room temperature with a 3 °C min^{-1} ramp. Two samples were prepared using two temperatures at 500 and 600 °C. Each sample is denoted using the preparation temperature.

2.2. Physical characterization

SEM and EDX investigations were carried out with a TESCAN Gaia 3 FIB/SEM system. Important components of the microscope are a 30 kV Triglav electron column and a Cobra focused gallium ion beam column. Two in-beam secondary electron (SE) and back scattered electron (BSE) detectors were used to obtain SEM images. EDX maps on the cross-sections were acquired by using the instrument EDAX HI-OCTANE detector. TEM and elemental mapping were performed employing a Talos™ F200X G2 TEM microscope (Thermo Scientific). Samples were prepared by suspending 1–2 mg of sample in 1 mL of isopropanol (ACS reagent, $\geq 99.5\%$ from Sigma Aldrich). The samples were sonicated for about 20 min. A drop of the suspension was then drop casted on a Holey TEM Copper grid, which was used as a sample holder for the characterization. XRD analysis was carried out using X'Pert PRO device (PANalytical) equipped with Co anode (wavelength $\text{K}\alpha_1$ 1.78901 Å).

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was performed with a UHV chamber (base pressure was lower than 10^{-9} mbar). The chamber was equipped with non-monochromatized Al radiation ($h\nu = 1486.6\text{ eV}$) and a hemispherical electron energy analyzer (VSW with a 16-channel detector). The X-ray source operated at 150 W (15 kV and 10 mA). The measurement of photoelectrons was carried out with the analyzer angle between the analyzer axis and X-ray source fixed at 54.5° . Samples were deposited onto carbon tape and XPS spectra were acquired in a fixed analyzer transmission mode with a fixed pass energy of 44.0 eV. CasaXPS software was used for spectra analysis with Linear or Shirley functions used to subtract the background. De-convolution was achieved using a combination of Gaussian and Lorentzian functions (70/30-ratio) and a Lorentzian Asymmetric function. Binding energies (B.E.) were calibrated by setting the C 1s component of the carbon tape to 285.1 eV [20]. The ex-situ Raman spectra were obtained with a Renishaw Raman spectrometer with a grating of 2400 grooves/mm in backscattering geometry with a 514 nm laser excitation wavelength. For the in-situ reduction, the precursor $\text{NiMoO}_4/\text{NiO}$ was placed in a high temperature Linkam stage (TS1200) at a set temperature of 630 °C under a 5 % H_2 95 % N_2 atmosphere. The Raman spectra of the reduced catalysts were measured on an in Via Renishaw Raman spectrometer with a 785 nm laser excitation wavelength and a grating of 1200 grooves/cm at 5 % laser power, corresponding to approximately 250 μW .

2.3. Electrochemical measurements

Milli-Q water was used to prepare the KOH 0.1 M solution, that was purged with N_2 or H_2 , for 30 min before the tests (all measurements were conducted under gas bubbling). Catalyst inks were composed of 5.8 mL^{-1} catalyst powder in 50:50 (v/v) water/ethanol containing 1 wt% of Nafion 5 wt%. The resulting suspension was ultrasonicated (59 Hz, 100 W) for 30 min. Electrochemical tests were conducted in a typical three-electrode system at 25 °C. The working electrode was prepared by drop-casting the ink suspension onto the glassy carbon area of the rotating disk electrode (RDE). The metal loading was determined using an analytical balance the amount of the dry deposit on the glassy carbon (area = 0.1964 cm^2). Ag/AgCl sat. electrode and Au wire were used as the reference and counter electrodes respectively. Cell potentials are reported using the RHE scale and potentials are corrected for electrolyte resistance using a fixed partial compensation of 75 % [21,22].

Parstat 2273 (Princeton Applied Research) was used to obtain electrochemical data. Hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) and hydrogen oxidation reaction (HOR) polarization curves were obtained by performing voltage scans between -0.2 and 0.2 V vs. RHE at 1 mV s^{-1} (RDE at 1600 rpm). Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS) was performed on working electrodes immersed in a 0.1 M KOH solution in a N_2 atmosphere. The frequency range was 100 kHz to 0.01 Hz. EIS spectra were obtained at 100 mV and at open circuit potential (OCP). “Zwiev4” and “EC lab” software were used for data analysis. Double-layer capacitance (Cdl) was calculated using cyclic voltammetry (1.0 M

KOH) using scan rates from 20 to 100 mV s⁻¹ over the potential range of 0.514 to 0.614 V (vs. RHE). The capacitor charging current j_c and discharging current j_d at 0.564 V were plotted against the scan rate (ν) using the equation: $|j| = \nu \times Cdl$, where Cdl is the slope of the linear fit.

2.4. Lab scale AEM water electrolysis cell testing

Catalyst coated electrodes were prepared by mixing 100 mg of MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600 °C catalyst powder with 100 mg aqueous PTFE suspension (10 wt%), and 60 mg Vulcan XC-72 carbon, a few drops of distilled water were added and mixed with the slurry until a fine paste is obtained. The paste was uniformly coated onto 5 cm² of Ni foam (Alantum Europe GmbH Germany – pore size 450 μm, AD 420 g m², Thickness 1.5 mm). The electrode was then wet proofed inside a quartz tube furnace at 350 °C for 15 min under N₂ flow.

Membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs), with the 5 cm² cathode and nickel foam anode electrodes were assembled together with a FAA-3-PK-130 membrane (Fumatech) using appropriate gaskets and graphite plate (cathode) and steel plate (anode) and tested using a stainless-steel Scribner test cell (Scribner Corp. USA). A 4 Nm torque closing force was used. The membrane and electrodes within the cell hardware were initially treated with 1 M KOH at 60 °C for 12 h. Arbin LBT21084 battery test station purchased from Arbin instruments was used for electrochemical measurements. An aqueous solution of KOH (1 M) was fed to the anode at 1 ml min⁻¹. The dry cathode compartment was connected to a Bronkhorst ELFlow flow meter to measure the H₂ produced. Linear scan voltage scans was undertaken from 0 and 2 V (10 mV s⁻¹). A constant current load of 1 A cm⁻² was applied to the cell to monitor changes in the cell voltage over time. The cell temperature for all measurements was maintained at 60 °C.

2.5. Scale up and large electrolysis cell testing

2.5.1. Catalyst ink preparation

The MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ 600 °C catalyst was mixed homogeneously with Vulcan XC-72 carbon at a ratio of 10:6 using planetary ball milling. Chloromethylated poly(styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene) block copolymer (PSEBS-CM) was used as both binding agent and ionomer in the catalyst layer. A catalyst to binder ratio of 9:1 was used to prepare the catalyst ink suspension in chloroform as solvent.

2.5.2. Electrode preparation

Membrane electrode assemblies (MEAs) were prepared using a catalyst coated substrate (CCS) method. The catalyst and ionomer mixture was applied to the surface of a Ni foam electrode using a sonication and dispersion deposition method. Cathode electrodes with an active surface area of 78.5 cm² (10 cm diameter disks) were prepared with a catalyst loading of 5 mg cm⁻². Prior to testing the electrodes were immersed in a 10 wt% DABCO (1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane) solution for 48 h at room temperature. This treatment introduces DABCO functional groups onto the PSEBS-CM polymer backbone conferring anionic conductivity to the catalyst layer [21,22]. The electrodes were then immersed in 0.1 mol dm⁻³ KOH solution to change the polymer binder to the conductive OH⁻ form. Anode electrodes were also prepared by this method. Ni foam coated with IrO₂ (2 mg cm⁻²) and NiCo₂O₄ spinel oxide catalysts (5 mg NiCo₂O₄ cm⁻²) were prepared.

2.5.3. Alkaline water electrolysis testing

A single electrolysis cell with an MEA active area of 78.5 cm² was used for testing. Electrochemical measurements were carried out with a modulab potentiostat (Ametek) equipped with 100 A booster. The membrane used for testing was an anion exchange polymer membrane PSEBS-CM-DABCO (dry thickness 60 μm). A 1 M aqueous solution of KOH was fed to the cell at a temperature of 50 °C. The electrodes were activated by applying a constant cell voltage of 1.9 V for NiCo₂O₄ anode and of 1.6 V for IrO₂ anode electrode respectively for 15 h. After the

activation procedure, short-term measurement of the load curves followed in cell voltage range 1.5–2.0 V. The cell voltage was increased step-wise using 0.05 V per step. Each point was measured for 60 s in order to reach steady state and between each point the cell was polarized by setting the voltage to 1.2 V for 60 s to remove bubbles. The load curves were accompanied by the determination of electrochemical impedance spectroscopy in the range from 1.3–1.8 V for the NiCo₂O₄ anode and in the range of 1.2–1.6 V for the IrO₂ anode. The amplitude was 10 mV and the frequency range was 100 kHz–0.1 Hz. The resistances were calculated using the equivalent electrical circuit shown in Fig. S1. Due to the absence of the second time constant for the NiCo₂O₄ anode, a simplified equivalent electrical circuit missing the Rp2 and CPE2 elements was used.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis and characterization

A commercial NiO nanopowder was used as substrate for the growth of NiMoO₄ nanorods using a hydrothermal synthesis in aqueous solution (150 °C for 6 h). This was followed by reductive annealing at high temperature (2 samples prepared at 500 and 600 °C respectively) under a flow of 5 % H₂/N₂ gas mixture. Treatment at temperatures above 600 °C generally leads to destruction of the rod structure and loss of activity and surface area [19]. ICP-OES analysis of the as-formed NiMoO₄ nanorods gave Mo 38.9 wt% and Ni 27.4 wt% (33.7 wt% O), while for MoO_{3-x}NiMoO₄ (600 °C) gave Mo 49.6 wt% and Ni 35.2 wt% (14.8 wt% O). We have already demonstrated that in this temperature range (500–600 °C) the most active materials are formed for the nickel foam supported material [19]. During the high temperature annealing treatment, the rod-shape structure is maintained, while the surface undergoes morphological and phase transformation. SEM images of the samples after synthesis confirm the rod structures and show how the starting NiMoO₄ develops a rougher surface as the high temperature reductive annealing treatment proceeds, with the formation of surface agglomerates and nanoparticles (Fig. 1a and 1b). The sample prepared at 600 °C has a visibly rougher surface than that formed at 500 °C. The formation of the typical rod-structure is also confirmed by TEM analysis (Fig. 2). The TEM image in Fig. 2a shows the formation of highly crystalline MoNiO₄ rods formed during hydrothermal synthesis and prior to the reductive annealing step. The NiO nanoparticles used as substrate for the synthesis are visible, embedded on the surface of the rod structures (see Fig. S2). XRD analysis of the powder indicates the formation of NiMoO₄ [23]. Interestingly, the hydrothermal synthesis was not successful in the absence of the NiO nano powder. Previously, we have reported the growth of NiMoO₄ rods on a nickel foam substrate [19].

Fig. S3 shows clearly how the smooth surface of the MoNiO₄ rods decomposes and transforms into a sponge-like structure after thermal annealing. Rather than forming a thin coating on the solid nickel foam substrate, the NiO seeded catalyst is a homogeneous nano powder composed of small-roughened rods. TEM images and elemental mapping reveal structural rearrangements and changes in the distribution of species. Fig. 2a shows a TEM image of NiMoO₄, which shows high crystallinity and the presence of the NiO nanopowder, which is proved by elemental distribution in Fig. S2. After the heat treatment at 500 or 600 °C a general roughening is observed for both samples. From elemental mapping, it can be seen that Mo tends to distribute homogeneously and even after the thermal treatments it appears well-dispersed (Fig. 2d and 2 h), while XPS shows an increase in Mo surface concentration (Table 1). Fig. 2c shows that Ni is less homogeneously dispersed on the surface, an effect that increases as the temperature rises (Fig. 2g). The NiO particles on the surface are reduced to Ni metal and combine with Ni from the precursor to form larger Ni particles, [24] forming seemingly crystalline structures as demonstrated by TEM bright field imaging in Fig. S4. These observations confirm that the reductive annealing causes a phase transition and the segregation of Mo to the

Fig. 1. SEM images of a) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C and b) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C.

Fig. 2. a) TEM image of precursor NiMoO_4 . b-e) STEM images and elemental mapping of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C, and f-i) STEM images and elemental mapping of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C.

Table 1

Molybdenum surface composition (%) for each sample by XPS.

	NiMoO_4	$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500 °C)	$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C)
Molybdenum %	9.3	10.1	10.9

surface. The XPS and Raman (Section 3.2) investigations point to the formation of a surface rich in MoO_{3-x} . This structure was also found to form on nickel foam supported Ni-Mo, which has undergone the same synthetic treatment [19].

The surface chemical composition of these materials was investigated by XPS (Fig. 3). The high-resolution Mo 3d signal is deconvoluted into four components at 227.9, 229.2, 230.4, and 232.2 eV corresponding to Mo(0), Mo(IV), Mo(V), and Mo(VI), respectively. The surface of the precursor NiMoO_4 is characterized by a mixture of Mo and Ni, with Mo present in the (VI) oxidation state. Nickel exists mostly in the oxidized form, with a small amount of Ni(0) present. These spectra correspond to the expected species NiMoO_4 . After high temperature reductive annealing, NiMoO_4 undergoes a process of dehydration and partial decomposition to form surface species such as MoO_2 and MoO_3 . Both samples at 500 °C and 600 °C clearly show a significant lowering of

the amount of Mo(VI) and at the same time an increase of Mo(IV) and Mo(V) signals. At 600 °C the presence of Mo(IV) is 36 %, implying the formation of a MoO_2 phase which is in accordance with the catalytic performance, as MoO_2 represents the main active species for the hydrogen evolution reaction. These spectroscopic results are consistent with the surface NiMoO_4 being partially reduced to MoO_2 . [20,25] XPS analysis also shows that the percentage of Mo on the surface increases (see tables S1, S2, S3) after the annealing treatments, in agreement with the previous work, in which a migration of Mo species occurred under the same conditions. [19] Nevertheless, a discrepancy emerges if we compare the formation of the different Mo oxidation states with the ones of the nickel foam supported catalysts. From Table S4 it is clear that Mo in $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ is more oxidized, with Mo(VI) at 60 % compared to 3 % for the Nickel foam material. Mo(V) remains quite similar especially for MoO_2/NiO 600 °C. It is interesting to note that Mo(IV) is present to a lesser extent for powder catalyst as well as metal Mo (Mo(0)) (Table S4). Regarding Ni, the metallic phase increases after heat treatment and was found to be more abundant in the 600 °C specimen (Fig. 3). The relative concentrations are listed in the Supporting Information (Tables S1, S2, S3). The reduction of the NiO nanoparticles to Ni metal occurs during reductive annealing so the presence of metallic nickel is not due to NiMo alloy formation as no metallic Mo is observed.

Fig. 3. XPS spectra of Mo and Ni for a-b) NiMoO_4 precursor, c-d) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C, e-f) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C.

3.2. In-situ Raman spectroscopy

In situ and ex situ Raman spectroscopy was used to probe the surface structural changes occurring during synthesis. The ex-situ room

Fig. 4. a) Room temperature Raman spectrum of the NiMoO_4 precursor. b) Spectra of the NiMoO_4 precursor as a function of temperature.

temperature Raman spectrum of the NiMoO_4 precursor is plotted in Fig. 4a. Clear Raman features are observed in the regions between 320–400 cm^{-1} and 770–980 cm^{-1} . NiMoO_4 exhibits polymorphism (α and β forms), β is the high temperature form with Mo in the tetrahedral environment [26]. The α form has Mo in the octahedral coordination, which exhibits characteristic Raman vibrations around 700 cm^{-1} [27]. Such a signature is clearly missing from the Raman spectrum indicating an absence of this phase in the material. Given the relatively low temperature synthesis and the instability of the β form at low temperatures, we predict that the precursor is in the hydrated phase of nickel molybdate ($\text{NiMoO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$). This is in agreement with various Raman studies of hydrated nickel molybdate, which exhibit high intensity modes around 356, 828, 870 and 947 cm^{-1} [28]. These modes correspond to the tetrahedral coordination of Mo that both $\text{NiMoO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\beta\text{-NiMoO}_4$ have in common. Modes below 400 cm^{-1} correspond to molybdenum-oxygen bending and the frequencies above 770 cm^{-1} to stretching, while the intense mode at 948 cm^{-1} is the symmetrical Mo-O stretching vibration [29].

It has been previously reported that heating hydrated nickel molybdate results in its transformation into the α form or β form round 400 °C [30]. We do not observe any new vibrational bands in the 700 cm^{-1} region with increasing temperature, Fig. 4b, indicating the absence of the α form. Around 500 °C the mode at 871 cm^{-1} disappears and a new mode at 881 cm^{-1} appears. This is similar to the spectra of $\beta\text{-NiMoO}_4$, which have been reported to have intense modes around 890 cm^{-1} [27]. Additionally, the intensity of the 356 mode shifts to 380 cm^{-1} around 500 °C. Bankar et al. measured the Mo-O bending mode in beta NiMoO_4 at 371 cm^{-1} , which is also upshifted in comparison to the hydrated NiMoO_4 [31]. We therefore conclude that the $\text{NiMoO}_4 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$ transforms from the hydrated to the β form at around 500 °C.

The reduction of the precursor was observed using in situ Raman spectroscopy is depicted in Fig. 5. The sample was heated in air to a set point of 630 °C when the 5% H_2 95% N_2 gas was purged through the stage and Raman spectra were measured as a function of time. The NiMoO_4 precursor modes are visible until about 20 min into the reduction, upon which they abruptly disappear, Fig. 5a. The intensities

Fig. 5. a) In-situ Raman spectroscopy of the reduction of NiMoO₄. Temperature set at 630 °C, Atmosphere switched to H₂:N₂ mix at T = 0. The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity and their intensity is normalized to their maximum intensity. Intensities b) and positions c) of the NiMoO₄ stretching modes as a function of reduction time.

of the spectra in Fig. 5a are normalized to visualize the very low intensity spectra of the reduced sample. The intensities of the precursor modes, Fig. 5b, decrease with reduction time signifying the reduced amount of the NiMoO₄ phase in the sample during reduction. However, the NiMoO₄ Raman peak positions remain constant, Fig. 5c. Usually, introduction of oxygen vacancies in metal oxides shifts their vibrational modes to lower frequencies as their bonds expand upon reduction [32]. Previous studies using in situ XRD and Raman during the reduction of α -NiMoO₄ did not find evidence of intermediate NiMoO_{4-x} suboxides [33,34]. This corroborates our results, that the reduction of NiMoO₄ results in a phase change rather than the accommodation of oxygen vacancies to form NiMoO_{4-x}. Rodriguez et al. suggested based on in situ XRD and XANES, that a rapid surface reduction of α -NiMoO₄ occurs above 325 °C, while reduction to metallic Mo proceeds only above 725 °C under hydrogen atmosphere [33]. These results are in good agreement with our measurements. The rapid reduction after 20 min

changes the surface color of the sample to black, which absorbs the Raman laser that cannot penetrate deeper into the sample.

To assign the phase of the reduced precursor, we measured Raman spectra of the catalysts reduced at 500 °C and 600 °C, Fig. 6. The spectra were taken with a Raman laser excitation wavelength of 785 nm, in order to increase the penetration depth of the dark samples. The laser energy was kept around 250 μ W to prevent sample heating that could lead to a reduction or oxidation of the material. In both spectra, we identify the remains of the NiMoO₄ precursor at frequencies above 850 cm⁻¹. Further we observe weak Raman modes around 189, 340, 714 and 815 cm⁻¹, Fig. 6. These agree with spectra of sub-oxides between MoO₃ and MoO₂, referenced here as MoO_{3-x}. [35]. The mode around 814 cm⁻¹ is a signature of the MoO₃ phase, meaning that the Mo(VI) oxidation state is present in the catalysts in the form of both MoO₃ and NiMoO₄. In conclusion, Raman predicts that the reduced catalyst contains remains of the NiMoO₄ precursor as well as suboxides of MoO_{3-x}, which is in good

Fig. 6. Raman spectra of the catalysts reduced at 500 °C and 600 °C, with reference to MoO₂ and MoO_{3-x} [35].

agreement with the XPS measurements.

3.3. Electrochemical characterization

The activity for the hydrogen evolution reaction (HER) was evaluated for both the samples $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ prepared at 500 and 600 °C, and also for a commercial Pt(40 %)/C as benchmark catalyst. In Fig. 7, linear scan voltammtries (LSV) are reported for the $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ samples. The material prepared at 600 °C shows the best performance in terms of mass activity and specific activity compared to $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C (Table 2). Electrochemical capacitance measurements are shown in Fig. 7c–d. An increase in the Cdl from 0.63 to 0.71 mF cm^{-2} occurs when the annealing temperature is increased from 500 to 600 °C that can be attributed to an increase in surface roughness as can be seen in the SEM images (Fig. 1). And, as stated before, a general Mo surface enrichment (Table 1), with the formation of more Mo(IV) species at 600 °C (Fig. 3), and homogenous presence of oxide species in TEM

micrographs (Fig. 2) prove that Mo is distributed uniformly. Catalytic activity cannot be explained by the presence of NiMo-alloys, as no trace of Mo(0) signal in the XPS spectra was found, this is accordance with the difficulty in reducing molybdenum at temperatures under 600 °C. [36,37] Increased activity can be explained by the increased surface area, and by the enhanced phase separation of MoO_{3-x} to the surface that occurs during heat treatment at 600 °C [38] and also to the presence of Ni/NiO interface that favors the Volmer–Heyrovsky or Volmer–Tafel processes [39]. Tafel analysis was also carried out for a more quantitative evaluation of the LSV data. The linear fitting of $\log J$ vs η curves are directly reported with respective Tafel slopes values in Fig. 7b. $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C), exhibits a lower Tafel slope for the HER compared to $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500 °C), and also a higher value of exchange current density for $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C) 3.24 $\text{A g}_{\text{Metal}}^{-1}$ (see Table 2), which reflect the improved activity compared to $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (500 °C). A direct comparison of the HER activity between $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ (600 °C) and the analogous material prepared on nickel foam (Fig. S6) confirms

Fig. 7. LSVs from HER to HOR region of $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 and 600 °C, 1 mV s^{-1} at 1600 rpm rotating disk. Inset shows the comparison in the HOR region. b) Tafel plots with relative Tafel slope for HER and HOR. Cdl measurement for c) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C and d) $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C. CVs recorded in the potential windows of 0.514 – 0.614 V vs. RHE with no faradaic processes. Cdl (Capacitance double layer) measurements were obtained by the slope of the capacitive current determined at 0.56 V as a function of scan rate (see insets). Nyquist plot obtained from impedance measurements at open circuit value e), and f) in HER region at –0.1 V vs RHE.

Table 2
Important electrochemical parameters obtained from LSV analysis.

	Specific activity [mA cm^{-2}] @ $\eta = 0.1$ V		Mass activity [$\text{A g}_{\text{Metal}}^{-1}$] @ $\eta = 0.1$ V		Exchange current [$\text{A g}_{\text{Metal}}^{-1}$]		Tafel slope [mV dec^{-1}]	
	HOR		HER	HOR	HER		HOR	HER
	$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C	0.07		0.11	0.48	0.76	0.30	169
$\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C	0.61		2.60	4.16	17.64	3.24	118.2	75
Pt(40 %)/C	3.11		25.8	32.88	272.32	16.45	74.6	43.1

the advantage of the synthesis using NiO as seed material compared to the Nickel foam approach, showing an increase in specific activity of 2.06 mA cm^{-2} @ -0.1 V vs RHE (Fig. S6). Impedance measurements were also recorded for $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ at 500 and 600 °C (Fig. 7e-f): EIS data were collected at open circuit potential (OCP) and in the region of the faradaic process of hydrogen evolution, at -0.1 V vs RHE. In the first case, Nyquist plot (Fig. 7e) shows high polarization resistance, which makes it difficult to recognize at low frequency the straight line at 45° typical of the diffusive phenomena described by Warburg element. In the HER region (Fig. 7f) instead, a semicircle at low frequency is observed for both samples, from here the value of charge transfer resistance (R_{ct}) was obtained. For $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 500 °C, R_{ct} is higher compared to $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C, 420 Ω and 134 Ω respectively. The R_{ct} value lowers and the activity rises, as pointed out by the polarization curve experiments. It is noteworthy that performing EIS at a lower potential of -0.05 V vs RHE, leads to an increase of the R_{ct} values in both cases (Fig. S7). For $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C the first semicircle at high frequency is not affected by the change in potential but only the one at low frequency (see Fig. S7), due to the fact that reaction kinetics are affected by the overpotential, it can be stated that semicircle at high frequencies is not related to the kinetics of the reaction [40,41]. In Table S5 the overpotential values for different materials are reported at -10 mA cm^{-2} , together with the materials reported here. $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C performs much better compared to QAMN (Quasi-Amorphous Metallic Nickel Nanopowder) 190 vs 240 mV, in KOH 0.1 M. Generally, the catalysts shown possess a similar activity even though the tests were performed in a much more concentrated electrolyte solution (KOH 1 M instead of KOH 0.1 M). In terms of performance $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C delivers current densities comparable to those present in literature when compared in less concentrated KOH solutions.

3.4. AEM water electrolysis cell testing

The lab scale AEM electrolysis cell with $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C as cathode and nickel foam as anode was evaluated through polarization curves from 0 to 2 V at 10 mV s^{-1} . The cell temperature was controlled at

60 °C. A typical polarization curve (Fig. 8a) shows that the system reaches 820 mA cm^{-2} at 2 V while $\text{MoO}_2/\text{Ni}_{\text{foam}}$ 600 °C from the previous work has recorded 517 mA cm^{-2} at the same cell voltage (see Fig. S11) [19]. Stability tests were also evaluated by running the cell for 50 h with a current load of 1 A cm^{-2} . In Fig. 8b, the trend of the curve shows stability is maintained after each replacement of fresh KOH solution. During the test the cell voltage oscillated around 2.2 V with a cell voltage-based energy cost of $57.7 \text{ kWh kg}^{-1} \text{ H}_2$. The MoO_2 on Ni foam cathode under the same conditions maintained stable operation at around 1.85 V at 0.5 A cm^{-2} [19]. From these tests it is clear the advantage of using a powder catalyst. This enhancement relates to improved mass specific catalytic activity and also to improved interfacial contact between the catalyst layer and the membrane, minimizing ohmic losses and improved charge transfer [42,43].

3.5. Large AEM electrolyser scale-up of electrode preparation and testing

Membrane-electrode assemblies (MEA) with an active area of 78.5 cm^2 were prepared using a catalyst coated substrate method. The catalyst layer, which is a mixture of catalyst particles and Vulcan-XC72 powder prepared by ball milling, was deposited on the surface of Ni foam by sonicated dispersion deposition method. Electrodes of geometrical area 78.5 cm^2 (10 cm diameter disks) were prepared with a catalyst loading of 5 mg cm^{-2} . The same method was used to prepare two types of anode electrodes; Ni foam coated with IrO_2 (2 mg cm^{-2}) and with NiCo_2O_4 spinel oxide catalysts ($5 \text{ mg NiCo}_2\text{O}_4 \text{ cm}^{-2}$). The catalyst layer contains a poly(styrene-ethylene-butylene-styrene) block copolymer (PSEBS-CM) acting as the polymer binder. The polymer also acts as anion conductor after treatment of the preformed electrode with DABCO that adds quaternary ammonium groups along the polymer chains that favour anion transport. Cathode and anode electrodes were assembled within the electrolysis cell hardware with an anion exchange polymer membrane PSEBS-CM-DABCO (thickness in dry state 60 μm). The cell temperature was 50 °C and 1 M aqueous KOH was fed to both anode and cathode compartments. The procedure used to obtain the load curves shown in Fig. 9 is described in the experimental section.

Fig. 8. a) Typical polarization curve for the AEM electrolysis cell at 60 °C, b) cell voltage monitored at 1 A cm^{-2} . AEMWE with $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode and Ni foam anode with Fumatech FAA-3-PK-130 AEM.

Fig. 9. Load curves of the alkaline water electrolysis with $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode and anodes using IrO_2 and NiCo_2O_4 catalyst. Temperature 50 °C, 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, PSEBS-CM-DABCO (60 μm thick) separator, 2 mg IrO_2 cm^{-2} , 5 mg NiCo_2O_4 cm^{-2} , geometrical area 78.5 cm^2 .

Fig. 9 shows the cell voltage versus current density curves for the cells with a PGM anode (IrO_2) and a non PGM anode (NiCo_2O_4). It is clear that the cell with IrO_2 anode outperforms the NiCo_2O_4 anode, achieving 0.9 A cm^{-2} at cell voltage 1.8 V. The same current density of 0.9 A cm^{-2} was achieved at 2.0 V using a non PGM NiCo_2O_4 anode catalyst. In our previous report, the nickel foam supported catalyst was also applied in the same up-scaled cell under similar conditions combined with a nickel foam connected as anode electrode. The cell reached 0.23 A cm^{-2} at 1.8 V. At 0.2 A cm^{-2} the cell operated at a stable voltage of 1.95 V over 60 h. These results confirm the advantage of catalysing the cathode electrode with the $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C powder compared to cathodes prepared by the growth of MoNi structures on the nickel foam structure.

Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy was used in order to obtain further insight into the performance of the tested electrodes. Values of ohmic (R_s) and polarisation resistances (R_p) evaluated from the measured spectra are shown in **Fig. 10**.

Fig. 10a shows that the cell with the IrO_2 based anode has a R_s 7 % lower than the NiCo_2O_4 cell. This small difference may be explained by higher electric conductivity of catalyst layer composed of IrO_2 catalyst when compared to catalyst layer utilizing NiCo_2O_4 . A more significant difference was observed for R_p values shown in **Fig. 10b**, which can be attributed to the reaction rate at the electrode surfaces. In the case of the NiCo_2O_4 catalyst only one semicircle is observed (**Fig. S10b**), while in the case of the IrO_2 catalyst, two semicircles are visible (**Fig. S10a**).

Due to slower kinetics and four-electron transfer (compared to two-electron HER), the R_p value of 1.51 Ω^2 for NiCo_2O_4 catalyst was

assigned to the OER reaction. In the case of the IrO_2 catalyst the two values of R_p are observed (0.13 and 0.04 Ω^2 respectively). These results indicate that the application of the non-PGM catalyst for OER was the limiting factor in the cell performance with a very high R_p values. On the other hand, the application of the more active IrO_2 catalyst resulted in decrease of the OER polarisation resistance to the extent that the effect of the cathode electrode resistance becomes observable in the EIS analysis. Lower polarisation resistance for the OER using the highly active IrO_2 catalyst accounts for the difference in cell performance and highlights the need for the development of highly active non PGM OER catalysts to match the performance of new non PGM cathode catalysts.

4. Conclusions

The combination of XPS, HR-TEM/STEM and in-situ Raman spectroscopy has enabled us to elucidate the surface structure of the material formed during the synthesis. Using commercially available NiO nanopowder as seed for the growth of the precursor enables the formation of a catalyst powder rather than a metallic electrode with a thin coating. The catalyst is hence composed entirely of the active phase and facilitates the application of the catalyst, improving the contact between the gas diffusion layer and the membrane with the concomitant increase in activity of MEAs. As expected, the temperature of reductive annealing is an important factor in optimizing the activity. At 600 °C the structure formed has a surface that is enriched in MoO_{3-x} and has increased roughness. The surface is characterized by agglomerated particles fused to the rod surface. In-situ Raman spectroscopy confirms the transformation from NiMoO_4 to MoO_{3-x} at high temperatures under H_2 . Electrochemical measurements demonstrate the improvement of performance compared to the analogous material prepared by the same procedure on Ni foam. A standard MEA of 5 cm^2 was then prepared and tested in an electrolyser cell using the $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ prepared at 600 °C. Stability test of 50 h at 1 A cm^{-2} was carried out while monitoring the H_2 produced, with a cell voltage-based energy cost of 57.65 kWh kg^{-1} H_2 . Lastly, scale-up water electrolysis cell was assembled, using an MEA of 78.5 cm^2 , this cell showed enhanced performance, reaching 0.9 A cm^{-2} at 1.8 V with an IrO_2 anode. When combined with a non PGM NiCo_2O_4 anode, 1 A cm^{-2} of electrolysis current density was produced at 2.0 V. In conclusion, we report a simple method to prepare a powder $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ catalyst that can be readily applied to electrode supports. Hence, scaling up of the catalyst synthesis and electrode preparation is facilitated, paving the way for the future application of such materials in larger AEM electrolysers.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Francesco Bartoli: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation. **Carolina Castello:** Investigation, Formal analysis. **Tailor Peruzzolo:** Investigation. **Enrico Berretti:** Investigation, Data curation.

Fig. 10. Results of ohmic resistance (a) (R_s) and (b) polarisation resistances (R_p) evaluated from EIS spectra. Temperature 50 °C, 1 mol dm^{-3} KOH, PSEBS-CM-DABCO (60 μm thick) separator, 2 mg IrO_2 cm^{-2} , 5 mg NiCo_2O_4 cm^{-2} $\text{MoO}_{3-x}\text{NiMoO}_4$ 600 °C cathode, geometrical area 78.5 cm^2 . EIS measured in the frequency range 100 kHz–10 Hz, with maximal amplitude 10 mV.

Eva Sediva: Investigation. **Karel Bouzek:** Supervision, Conceptualization. **Jaromir Hnat:** Investigation. **Michaela Plevova:** Investigation. **Lorenzo Poggini:** Investigation, Data curation. **Hamish Andrew Miller:** Conceptualization, Data curation, Formal analysis, Funding acquisition, Supervision, Writing – original draft.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgements

This research was funded by NextGeneration EU from the Italian Ministry of Environment and Energy Security POR H2 AdP MMES/ENEA with involvement of CNR and RSE, PNRR - Mission 2, Component 2, Investment 3.5 “Ricerca e sviluppo sull'idrogeno” L.A.3.1.6, CUP: B93C22000630006. This study was also supported by the European Regional Development Fund Project “Fuel Cells with Low Platinum Content” (no. CZ.02.1.01/0.0/0.0/16.025/0007414). This publication was supported by the project “The Energy Conversion and Storage”, funded as project No. CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004617 by Programme Johannes Amos Comenius, call Excellent Research. We also thank Brunetto Cortigiani for his assistance in using the “MatchLab” platform at the University of Florence.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2025.162026>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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